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Physics-Based, Data-Augmented Model for Wind Turbine Control Design

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Abstract. Accurate modeling of wind turbine dynamics is essential, as it enables engineers to design optimized control systems that enhance the performance and reliability of wind turbines. This study demonstrates how a hybrid model, integrating physics-based equations and a data-driven neural network, outperforms both low-fidelity physics models and purely data-driven approaches in estimating rotational speed with higher accuracy. By leveraging fundamental physical principles to capture key aerodynamic and mechanical behaviors and incorporating machine learning to estimate effective wind speed, the hybrid approach addresses the limitations of traditional methods. Purely physics-based models often struggle with uncertainties and variability in real-world conditions, while data-driven models lack generalizability and fail to incorporate physical constraints. In contrast, the hybrid model combines the strengths of both approaches, ensuring consistency with physical laws while adapting to operational variability. Validation using the high-fidelity OpenFAST simulation environment highlights the potential of the hybrid model not only for accurate dynamic modeling but also as a foundation for future model-based optimal control designs.

1 Introduction

The growing impact of the global greenhouse effect has led to a significant increase in global efforts to eliminate greenhouse gas emissions by 2050 [1]. Historically, fossil fuels have been the primary energy source worldwide, but their overuse has raised serious environmental concerns. In response, there has been a consistent move towards adopting clean and sustainable energy alternatives. Among these alternatives, wind energy stands out due to its vast availability, cost-effectiveness, and minimal environmental impact, playing a crucial role in the transition to a sustainable energy landscape [2]. Wind power technology has experienced rapid advancements in the 21st century, leading to considerable growth in both onshore and offshore wind capacities. According to the World Wind Energy Association's 2023 Annual Report, the total installed global wind power capacity has surpassed 1,047 GW, with an additional 116 GW added in 2023, signifying a robust growth rate of 12.5% [3]. These developments highlight the crucial role of wind energy in achieving sustainable global energy goals and highlight the pressing need for innovative strategies to improve the efficiency, reliability, and operational performance of wind energy technologies, particularly wind turbines [4].

The ability to effectively model wind turbines plays a fundamental role in ensuring their optimal performance and long-term reliability. From a control systems standpoint, reliable models enable operators to execute more effective control strategies [5]. Moreover, modeling supports the forecasting of

system states and the continuous monitoring of operational parameters, which are vital for proactive maintenance and performance optimization [6]. Research on wind turbine modeling mostly focuses on two main approaches. The first approach uses physical equations derived from aerodynamic and mechanical theories to simulate turbine behavior. The problem with these physical models is that they can be inaccurate due to system uncertainties. The second approach relies on data-driven models that utilize machine learning algorithms to analyze operational data. Although these algorithms are effective in modeling complex patterns, they might lack the ability to generalize to new, unseen data, limiting their usefulness in diverse operational contexts [7]. To overcome these challenges, hybrid models have been introduced, combining the strengths of both physical and data-driven techniques.

In the literature, there are various ways to combine machine learning algorithms with physical equations. The most well-known approach is physics-informed neural networks, where cost functions and constraints derived from physics ensure that the neural network finds a solution consistent with physical laws [8]. For example, in [9], a physics-informed neural network was developed to integrate the physical constraints of wind turbine systems into the data-driven model. By integrating structural physical constraints into a deep residual recurrent neural network, the model reduces computational costs and improves accuracy compared to purely data-driven methods. Another approach is using a corrective term for a physical model with a data-driven model. For example, in [10], a hybrid two-stage deep learning framework is proposed to reconstruct urban wind fields. Significant accuracy improvements in the prediction of complex wind fields are achieved by integrating a computational fluid dynamics-based physical feature extraction model with sparse measurement-based error correction. Furthermore, incorporating input from physical equations into a data-driven model is another technique. For instance, in [11], physical equations were used to estimate wind turbine control actions by adding additional inputs to a data-driven model, thereby enhancing the prediction accuracy.

The main contribution of this study is the design of a novel hybrid framework—a physics-based approach that integrates a data-driven component specifically aimed at estimating rotor-effective wind speed. The data-driven component employs a simple neural network with low execution time, making it suitable for real-time applications within a control system. By combining physical equations with machine learning methods, the hybrid model compensates for uncertainties inherent in physical models and enhances its ability to generalize across various operating conditions.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 discuss the wind turbine under study. Section 3 outlines the methodology, encompassing the physical modeling, data-driven modeling, and the development of the hybrid physics-based, data-augmented model. Section 4 presents the results. Finally, in Section 5, the conclusion is presented along with a discussion of potential future research directions.

2 System under study

In this study, the wind turbine is modeled using OpenFAST, a software developed by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) [12]. OpenFAST employs a modular framework, with each module utilizing high-fidelity physical equations to simulate turbine dynamics in a coordinated manner [12]. The selected wind turbine for analysis in this software is the 5 MW NREL reference wind turbine. This wind turbine serves as a benchmark for numerous research applications due to its detailed design specifications, making it ideal for validating models and developing control systems. This turbine features a three-blade, upwind rotor system with a rotor diameter of 126 meters. The hub is positioned 90 meters above the ground, supported by a hollow cylindrical tower, providing structural stability and flexibility under various loading conditions [13]. Table 1 presents the key parameters of this wind turbine.

To ensure the efficient operation of the 5 MW NREL wind turbine, it is essential to implement effective controllers that can manage the turbine's behavior across different operating regions. An effective controller for the OpenFAST simulation environment is the NREL Reference Open-Source Controller (ROSCO) [14]. ROSCO is an advanced control system developed for wind turbines, designed to simplify controller tuning while aligning with standard industry practices. It is designed to maximize power production in below-rated wind speeds and regulate rotor speed in above-rated conditions, ensuring optimal performance across different operating regions. Figure 1 shows the steady-state responses of this wind turbine in different operating regions. In Region 1, when the wind speed is below the cut-in speed of 3 m/s, the turbine remains inactive. In Region $1\frac{1}{2}$, between the cut-in and rated wind speeds, the turbine operates in variable-speed mode, increasing power output as wind speed rises from 3 m/s to 11.4 m/s. In Region 2, the turbine continues in variable-speed operation, optimizing power capture by adjusting the rotor speed to match the wind speed. As the wind nears the rated speed in Region $2\frac{1}{2}$, the system transitions to pitch control to maintain a consistent power output. Finally, in Region 3, when wind speeds exceed the rated level, the turbine operates at its rated power, with pitch control regulating aerodynamic power capture and controlling rotor speed [13, 14].

Table 1. Parameters of 5 MW NREL Wind Turbine

Parameter	5 MW NREL
Rated Power	5,000 kW
Rated Wind Speed	11.4 m/s
Cut-in Wind Speed	4 m/s
Cut-off Wind Speed	30 m/s
Rated Rotor Speed	12.1 rpm
Rotor Diameter	126 m
Hub Height	90 m
Gear box ratio	97:1
Generator Inertia	534.116 kg·m ²
Rotor Inertia	38,677,056 kg·m ²
Drivetrain Torsional-Spring Constant	867,637,000 N·m/rad
Drivetrain Torsional-Damping Constant	6,215,000 N·m/(rad/s)

Figure 1: Steady-state response of 5 MW NREL wind turbine using ROSCO controller: (a) Generator characteristics and rotor power output, (b) Aerodynamic control response

3 Methodology

3.1 Physical Modeling

One approach to modeling a wind turbine is to rely solely on fundamental physics. Accordingly, the aerodynamic torque of a wind turbine can be determined by the following equation:

$$T_r = \frac{1}{2} \rho A v^3 C_p(\lambda, \beta) / \omega_r \quad (1)$$

$$\lambda = \frac{R \cdot \omega_r}{v} \quad (2)$$

where ρ is air density, v is wind speed, A is the swept area of the wind turbine, ω_r is rotational speed, and C_p is the power coefficient. It is clear that controlling β directly regulates T_r and can also be influenced indirectly by generator torque, yaw, etc. This torque is calculated using the AeroDyn module in OpenFAST by integrating drag and lift forces across the blade, taking into account wind speed and direction at different nodes. After that, the calculated aerodynamic torque will be an input for the ElastoDyn module, where it will be used to simulate the dynamic response of the wind turbine. Depending on the degrees of freedom considered, the rotor speed can be calculated using different physical equations. For instance, consider a simple model of the wind turbine (one inertia model), in which the rotor is treated as a rigid body:

$$J_{eq} \dot{\omega}_r = T_r - T_g \cdot N \quad (3)$$

$$J_{eq} = J_r + J_g \cdot N^2 \quad (4)$$

where J_{eq} is the equivalent moment of inertia of the rotor and generator, ω_r is the rotor speed, T_r is the aerodynamic torque, and T_g is the generator torque [15]. It should be noted that in this study, the term 'rotor' specifically refers to the 'turbine rotor'. In addition, considering drivetrain rotational-flexibility (two inertia model), the following equations can be used [16]:

$$(J_r + J_g N^2) \ddot{\theta}_r - J_g N^2 \ddot{\nu} = T_r - T_g \cdot N \quad (5)$$

$$-J_g N^2 \ddot{\theta}_r + J_g N^2 \ddot{\nu} + K\nu + B\dot{\nu} = T_g \cdot N \quad (6)$$

where J_r is the inertia of the rotor, J_g is the inertia of the generator, N is the gear ratio between the rotor and generator, θ_r is the rotor angle, θ_g is the generator angle, T_r is the torque applied to the rotor, T_g is the torque applied to the generator, K is the drivetrain torsional spring, B is the drivetrain torsional damper, and ν is the torsion angle between the two angles:

$$\nu = \frac{\theta_r - \theta_g}{N} \quad (7)$$

Differentiating ν with respect to time, we get:

$$\dot{\nu} = \dot{\theta}_r - \frac{\dot{\theta}_g}{N}; \ddot{\nu} = \ddot{\theta}_r - \frac{\ddot{\theta}_g}{N} \quad (8)$$

Substituting $\ddot{\nu}$ into the original system:

$$(J_r + J_g N^2) \ddot{\theta}_r - J_g N^2 \left(\ddot{\theta}_r - \frac{\ddot{\theta}_g}{N} \right) = T_r - T_g \cdot N \quad (9)$$

$$-J_g N^2 \ddot{\theta}_r + J_g N^2 \left(\ddot{\theta}_r - \frac{\ddot{\theta}_g}{N} \right) + K \left(\theta_r - \frac{\theta_g}{N} \right) + B \left(\dot{\theta}_r - \frac{\dot{\theta}_g}{N} \right) = T_g \cdot N \quad (10)$$

Simplifying these equations:

$$J_r \ddot{\theta}_r + J_g N \ddot{\theta}_g = T_r - T_g \cdot N \quad (11)$$

$$-J_g N \ddot{\theta}_g + K \theta_r - \frac{K \theta_g}{N} + B \dot{\theta}_r - \frac{B \dot{\theta}_g}{N} = T_g \cdot N \quad (12)$$

Solving for the angular accelerations $\ddot{\theta}_r$ and $\ddot{\theta}_g$:

$$\ddot{\theta}_g = \dot{\omega}_g = \frac{K \left(\theta_r - \frac{\theta_g}{N} \right) + B \left(\dot{\theta}_r - \frac{\dot{\theta}_g}{N} \right) - T_g \cdot N}{J_g N} \quad (13)$$

$$\ddot{\theta}_r = \dot{\omega}_r = \frac{T_r - T_g \cdot N - J_g N \ddot{\theta}_g}{J_r} \quad (14)$$

It is evident that in both the one-inertia and two-inertia models, adjusting T_g will result in changes to the rotor speed. In this study, a two-inertia model was used to achieve a more realistic representation of the drivetrain's behavior and dynamics.

3.2 Data-driven Modeling

In this section, the structure of the implemented data-driven model is presented. To generate data, OpenFAST with the ROSCO controller needs to be tested across a wide range of wind profiles. To achieve this, a code for data extraction, as shown in Code 1, is developed. Here, wind profiles are generated using TurbSim [17]. These wind profiles are then fed into OpenFAST, and the outputs of interest are recorded. In the simulations, 100 wind profiles are generated using the IEC 61400 standard with turbulence intensity category B. In this analysis, it was presumed that the wind was perfectly aligned with the turbine's hub axis, with no yaw misalignment or divergence between the turbine's orientation and the wind direction. Each simulation lasts 600 seconds with a time step of 0.01 seconds. A total of 80 operating points are used for the training dataset, while 20 are reserved for the test dataset. Figure 2 shows the collected data for the test dataset.

Code 1: Data extraction for different wind profiles using OpenFAST

1. Define constants, including file paths and parameters (U_{Ref} , Rand , and the number of operating points to be generated).
2. Generate random U_{Ref} values within the specified range of 5 to 25 m/s.
3. For each U_{Ref} value, generate a random Rand value.
4. Update the TurbSim input file with the current U_{Ref} and Rand values.
5. Run TurbSim and capture the output.
6. Prepare the `InflowWind` file for each run by updating the wind file reference.
7. Update the `.fst` file to reference the new `InflowWind` file.
8. Run OpenFAST with the updated `.fst` file and capture the output.
9. Rename the OpenFAST output file for each run.
10. Clean up by deleting temporary files.

Note: U_{Ref} is the mean of wind speed, and Rand is the seed value used to create a unique wind profile in TurbSim. Additionally, `.fst` files serve as the primary input files in OpenFAST.

Figure 2: Generated data for test dataset: (a) Wind speed at hub, (b) Generator torque, (c) Blade pitch angle, (d) Rotor speed.

3.3 Hybrid Physics-Based, Data-Augmented Model

In this section, the structure of the proposed hybrid physics-based, data-augmented model is discussed. This model is designed to combine the strengths of both physics-based models and data-driven techniques to enhance the accuracy and robustness of wind turbine control strategies.

Here, we assume that the physical parameters of the wind turbine represent the ground truth values, as shown in Table 1. Reconsider Equation 1. The issue with the physical model is that v , the wind speed, should represent the average rotor-effective wind speed across entire swept area, rather than the hub wind speed or any other measured wind speed. However, the average rotor-effective wind speed cannot be directly measured; it is a response derived from the entire wind turbine system. Therefore, we first calculate the average effective rotor wind speed at different operating points, relying on known physical parameters. We will then apply a data-driven component to estimate the effective wind speed for unknown operating points.

The approach begins by using physical parameters such as turbine inertia, gearbox ratio, and blade radius of the NREL 5 MW reference wind turbine. With these known values and the fundamental physical equations, an inverse data extraction methodology is applied to calculate the effective wind speed. Figure 3 shows the flowchart of the process for developing a hybrid model by integrating data-driven and physics-based approaches, beginning with data extraction using OpenFAST and ending with the integration of neural network-based components with physical equations.

Figure 3: Flowchart of the hybrid model development process.

The following steps outline the process:

1. Aerodynamic Torque Calculation: The aerodynamic torque is calculated using a numerical solver. The aerodynamic torque can be obtained from measurements of rotor speed and generator torque. Here, it is assumed that inertia values are known parameters.

2. **Effective Wind Speed Estimation:** Once the aerodynamic torque is determined, the model applies the well-established relationships between aerodynamic forces, rotor speed, and wind speed to estimate effective wind speed. The power coefficient (C_p) is a key factor here, as it defines the efficiency of the wind turbine in converting wind energy into mechanical energy. These values are calculated based on predefined C_p lookup tables of 5MW NREL wind turbine. The effective wind speed is calculated for each operating point using Equation 1, with the goal of determining the rotor-effective wind speed, V_{e_k} .
3. **Neural Network Integration:** Instead of directly predicting the rotor speed as in traditional data-driven models, the hybrid model takes a more nuanced approach by configuring the neural network to predict the effective wind speed. This step allows the model to incorporate physical constraints while using data-driven methods to enhance its prediction capabilities. The neural network, trained on operating data from multiple scenarios, uses the predicted effective wind speed to estimate the rotor speed indirectly through the physical model. The rationale behind this approach is that effective wind speed can capture dynamic changes more accurately than direct rotor speed predictions.

Figure 4 shows the structure of the final three models.

Figure 4: Wind turbine Models: (a) Physical Model, (b) Data-driven Model, (c) Hybrid Physics-based, Data-augmented Model.

4 Results

In this section, the performance of the developed hybrid physics-based data-augmented model is compared with a low-fidelity physics-based model, a purely data-driven model, and the high-fidelity OpenFAST model. Figure 5 shows the performance of the data-driven model and the data-driven component of the hybrid model. Since we employed a simple neural network with two hidden layers, the training time was only 170 seconds on a PC with a 13th Gen Intel® Core™ i7-1365U 1.80 GHz processor. Furthermore, processing the entire test dataset took just 0.15 seconds, demonstrating that the model can be integrated into a control framework for real-time operation. In the data-driven model, the rotor speed is directly predicted, while in the hybrid model, the effective average wind speed is predicted, which is then used to estimate rotor speed through the physical approach. The figures indicate that the neural network can more effectively follow the trends in the effective wind speed, compared to predicting the rotor speed directly.

Figure 5: Comparison of neural network prediction with actual values for test data: (a) Rotor speed prediction or data-driven model (b) Wind speed prediction or data-driven component of hybrid model.

To enable a more accurate comparison between different models, two different operating points were selected among all operating points in test data set: one in Region 2, where the mean wind speed at the hub is 10 m/s, and one in Region 3, where the mean wind speed at the hub is 15 m/s. Figures 6 and 7 show the effective wind speed, predicted effective wind speed, and measured wind speed at the hub, as well as a comparison of different models for Regions 2 and 3, respectively. Moreover, Figure 8 shows the probability density function for both regions. Finally, Table 2 shows the MSE and RMSE values for rotor speed prediction in both regions using the following equations:

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\omega_i - \hat{\omega}_i)^2 \quad (15)$$

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\omega_i - \hat{\omega}_i)^2} \quad (16)$$

where ω_i is the actual rotor speed from the high-fidelity OpenFAST model, and $\hat{\omega}_i$ is the predicted rotor speed using different models. It can be seen that the proposed hybrid model consistently outperformed the low-fidelity model and data-driven model in both regions. In addition to the MSE and RMSE comparisons, the probability density function provides further insight into model performance. The results indicate that the hybrid model yields a narrower error distribution, suggesting that it captures the rotor speed trends more effectively.

Figure 6: Region 2: (a) Wind speed prediction, (b) Comparison of rotor speed predictions across models

Figure 7: Region 3: (a) Wind speed prediction, (b) Comparison of rotor speed predictions across models

Figure 8: Comparison of probability density function: (a) Region 2, (b) Region 3

Table 2. Comparison of MSE and RMSE for two chosen operating points across different models compared to High-fidelity OpenFAST

Model	Region 2		Region 3	
	MSE	RMSE	MSE	RMSE
Low-fidelity Model	0.0654	0.2558	0.0509	0.2255
Data-driven Model	0.0398	0.1995	0.0088	0.0938
Hybrid Model	0.0326	0.1807	0.0021	0.0456

5 Conclusion

In conclusion, this study has developed a hybrid model for predicting rotational speed that can be incorporated into predictive control approaches by integrating physics-based and data-driven methodologies. The hybrid model leverages the strengths of both approaches, addressing the limitations of purely physics-based models in capturing real-world complexities and uncertainties, while avoiding the generalization issues of purely data-driven models. Using this combined approach, the model is better equipped to estimate the rotor speed and handle unmodeled dynamics, particularly in highly variable wind conditions. Although the current implementation relies on a multilayer perceptron neural network configuration, future work could explore more advanced data-driven techniques to estimate the unknown uncertainties within the physical equations. These techniques have the potential to further enhance model predictions by complementing and building upon the current approach. More accurate models can lead to optimized control actions, which are crucial for efficient and reliable wind turbine operations, particularly in model predictive control frameworks. In addition, incorporating a physical parameter estimation framework into the model can enhance its robustness against uncertainties in the physical parameters.

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